

Relationship between Journal Impact Factor and the Thoroughness and Helpfulness of Peer Reviews

Details about the Reproduction Materials (Version: 4 July 2023)

This repository, hosted at Zenodo, contains the code and data used to reproduce summary statistics, plots, and tables reported in the main paper and S1 Files.

Due to Clarivate's/Publons' data-sharing policies, we cannot upload datasets containing the review texts. However, we provide the entire code to ensure transparency regarding the workflow and classification. We also release the fine-tuned DistilBERT models. The repository also contains all outputs (i.e., tables and plots). Below, we describe the relevant files and classifiers.

Fine-tuned DistilBERT models

The fine-tuned DistilBERT classifiers are in the repository in the zip file `distilbert_models.zip`, containing eight subfolders. The name of each folder describes the classifier.

- `criticism`: Criticism
- `example`: Example
- `importance_and_relevance`: Importance and Relevance
- `materials_and_methods`: Materials and Methods
- `praise`: Praise
- `presentation_and_reporting`: Presentation and Reporting
- `results_and_discussion`: Results and Discussion
- `suggestion_and_solution`: Suggestion and Solution

The file `00_tutorial_apply_models.html` shows how to apply the eight classifiers to sentences and store the predicted class for the eight content categories.

Replication data and code

Below, we describe each code script, the datasets loaded in each script, and the outputs of each file. We recommend using RStudio and creating an RProject¹ in the folder that includes all scripts and datasets. Otherwise, users can adjust their working directory manually using `setwd("path/to/folder")` or the **here**² package.

`01_main_paper.R`: code to reproduce all analyses reported in the main paper.

- **Datasets**: `data_all_wide_bert.csv` (available in the repository: classified and aggregated data for each review, resulting in 10,000 observations); `dat_classified_with_sentences_bert.rds` (not available due to data sharing policies; contains classified raw texts on the level of sentences; used to get summary statistics mentioned in the text)

`02_s1_file.R`: code to create tables and plots in S1 File

¹ <https://support.posit.co/hc/en-us/articles/200526207-Using-RStudio-Projects>

² <https://here.r-lib.org>

- **Datasets:** `data_all_wide_bert.csv` (available in the repository: classified and aggregated data for each review, resulting in 10,000 observations); `dat_classified_with_sentences_bert.rds` (not available due to data sharing policies; contains classified raw texts on the level of sentences)

`03_s2_file.R`: code to create plots in S2 File

- **Datasets:** `data_all_wide_bert.csv` (available in the repository: classified and aggregated data for each review, resulting in 10,000 observations); `data_classes_trainingset.csv` (available in the repository: dataset indicating which category/categories each sentence from the training set falls into; does not contain any identifying information); `data_bert_test_small_...csv` (eight datasets that contain the sentences and predictions for the held-out test set (not available due to data sharing policies)); `data_categories_coder_01.xlsx` and `data_categories_coder_02.xlsx` (available in the repository; coding of sentences used for fine-tuning classifiers; due to data sharing policies, the text of each observation cannot be included in these datasets)

`04_s3_file.R`: code to run all sensitivity analyses reported in S3 File.

- **Datasets:** `data_all_wide_bert.csv` (available in the repository: classified and aggregated data for each review, resulting in 10,000 observations)

`function_theme_base.R`: custom ggplot2 scheme; loaded in most files

Note: S4 File only contains the codebook and no plots or tables. Therefore, we do not provide an R script for replication purposes.

Package versions used to reproduce the analyses are reported at the beginning of each script.